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Climate Change and Environmental Education A key to Sustainable Primary School Pupils: An Overview

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ABSTRACT

This study is focused on a review of environmental education and climate change awareness in the primary school sector. Various concepts and definitions have been discussed primarily to enable us have firm understanding of the concepts with respect to the polluted and or over exploited resources in the environment. In the reviews of the literatures, it was observed that the priority of such education is to developing cautious mind of the pupils at the lower level about their total surrounding. Its main task is to impact proper knowledge and training to solve problems of our environment systematically. Teaching primary school pupils by including climate change curriculum will create early awareness of the pros and cons in the environment they grow up with. This will enable then understand better than in their adult stage, and will enable proper management of the environmental ethics.

Keywords: Climate change, Environment, Education, Primary School, Pupils,

INTRODUCTION

Education is utilized in three perspectives (Knowledge, Subject and as a Process). That is, when an individual achieved an academic qualification up to a certain level we do not call it education. For instance, if an individual or a person has secured Master degree then we utilize education in a very narrow sense and call that the person has achieved education up to Master Level. In the second perspective, education is utilized in a sense of discipline, if a person had taken education as a paper or as a discipline during his study in any institution, then we utilize education as a subject. Lastly, education is utilized as a process. We talk what is education as a process. In fact in this context, the research interest is to discuss education as a process on climate change issues. This study is divided into five sections. Section one, reviews the concept of education and environmental education; two, the concept of climate change and its effects, three climate change through quality education, four. Primary school pupils, and five summary and conclusion.

Concept of Education and Environmental Education. Education is not merely acquiring of knowledge, gathering and correlating facts; it is to see the significance of life as a whole. But the whole cannot be approached through the part, which is what government, organized religions and authoritarian parties are attempting to do (Kumar & Gandhi, 1974). The basic realm of social progress involves the activities to transform nature, society and man (Vikoo, 2015 & 2016). Researchers at various times attempted to explain the concept of education and stated the relationship between instruction and other areas of inquiry within education and stated that the objective of education vary from society to society based on the problems and needs of the particular society (Regolith 1983; Vikoo, 2015). Plethora of the definition of the term 'education' exists. Kumar and Ahmad stated fourteen definitions, and from the perspective of this research four definitions are of great concern. 1) 'By education it means an all-round drawing out of

the best in child and man's body, mind and spirit'. 2) 'Education is the child's development from within. 3) 'Education is the complete development of the individuality of the child so that he can make an original contribution to human life according to the best of his ability' and, 4) 'Education is not a preparation for life, rather it is the living. Education is the process of living through a continuous reconstruction of experiences. It is the development of all those capacities in the individual which will enable to control his environment and fulfill his possibilities'. The meaning and definitions of education stated above lead to the conclusion that education should have a comprehensive definition. Education may be defined as a purposive, conscious or unconscious, psychological, sociological, scientific and philosophical process, which brings about the development of the individual to the fullest extent and also the maximum development of society in such a way that both enjoy maximum happiness and prosperity. Education is the process of changing the behavior pattern of people, the way through which people are changing their thinking, their feelings and their overt actions (Peter, 2010). In other words, education implies showing the way to lead and is a process by which persons or group of persons acquiring new knowledge or experience. Education implies experience (Peter, 2010, Obiene, 2016). This means that the result of good education should be able to play meaningful part on the preservation, transmission, transformation (where necessary) of values, and should be able to contribute to the solution of problem in the society. Thus, education is seen as the pivot on which the prosperity and future of any community, state or nation depends.

Different thinkers have given their own definitions of education; the concept of education can be analyzed from the view point of various theoretical stands on education. In the positivist perspective, the philosophy of education is concerned with what is said about education by those who practice it (teachers) and by those who theorize about the individual theorists (Moore, 1982). Moore regards education as a group of activities going on at various logical levels. Logical in the sense that each higher level arises out of and is dependent on or below it. The lowest level is the level of educational practice at which activities like teaching, instructing, motivation pupils, etc, are carried on. It involves the lowest levels such as teachers talked about teaching, learning, knowledge and experience. The other aspect of educational theory is one which described the role of or function of education, rather it makes specific recommendations about those engaged in educational practice ought to be doing (practical theories). Theories of this nature exhibit a wide variety in scope, content, and complexity and are called theories of teaching (pedagogical theories). These theories postulate that "teachers should make sure that any new materials introduced to pupils should be linked to what they already know or that "a child should not be told a fact before he has had a chance to find out for himself". This is an example of prescriptive theories. In the Environmental Education, environmental problems are one of the most dangerous threats for current and future generations (Kotaman et al., 2022) UNCED (1992) stated that Environmental issues should be handle globally because environmental protection is interdependent and indivisible (UNCED1992). Kotaman et al (2022) and the United Nations have stated that many international treaties such as Rio, 1992, Kyoto, 1997, Rio, 2012 have been signed by countries all around the world. In these and other international platforms, the need for raising new generations with environmental awareness mentally has always been emphasized. However, since education is the main tool for societies to raise future citizens of the world, it is reasonable to expect integration of environmental issues in the education system (Kotaman, 2022), particularly when it relates to climate change perception.

Environment generally consists of two main aspects natural and man-made or social. The study of the interactions between the man, the natural and social environment is called 'environmental education' (Kumar (2021). It is the biophysical (outer system) in which people and organisms exist. Generally, the word environment is used to refer to anything, living or non-living that surrounds and influences living organisms and Environmental education is an integral process which deals with man's interrelationship with his natural and man-made surrounding's including the relation of particular growth. Environmental education may best be defined as a process directed at creating awareness and understanding about environmental issues that leads to responsible individual and group actions. Environmental education is a learning process that increases people's knowledge and awareness about the environment and associated

challenges, develops the necessary skills and expertise to address the challenges and fosters attitudes, motivations, and commitments to make informed decisions and the responsible action. Environmental education is the process of recognizing values and clarifies concepts related to environment and its problems in order to develop skill and attitudes necessary to understand the environment (Kumar, 2021; Eugene, 2005). It entails practice in decision making and self-formulating a code of behavior about issues concerning environmental quality. Environmental education refers to organized efforts to teach how natural environments function, and particularly, how human beings can manage behavior and ecosystems to live sustainably. It is a multidisciplinary field (Kumar, 2021) integrating discipline such as biology, chemistry, physics, ecology, earth science, atmospheric science, mathematics, and geography. The term often implies education within the school system, from primary to post-secondary. Since the integration of environmental education issues in the educational system, for instance, in the Rio, 1992, Agenda 21 pointed to the critical role of education (Kotaman et al., 2022), it help in promoting sustainable development and improving the ability of people to address environmental and development issues (Kotaman et al., 2022; Seikkula-Leino et al., 2021, Kumar, 2021; UNCED, 1992). Kotaman (2022) opined that since it is obvious to implement environmental education, the first thing to do is to prepare teachers. Teachers should be qualified to provide environmental education. Their success in raising citizens with environmental awareness largely depends on teachers' competence about delivering about environmental education (climate change). In developing the necessary pathways for dealing with, and preventing global problems, the concept of education was emphasized. Gazzaz & Aldeseet, (2021), pointed out that, the case of problems arising from man-made climate change; the concept of climate change education was developed. This according to Gazzaz & Aldeseet, (2021), climate change education is a relatively new discipline of education that has quickly established itself given the urgency of the climate crisis. Climate change education finds its root primarily in environmental, sustainability education, and science education. The relatively new discipline is designed to equip students (primary pupils, for instance) with the knowledge, skills and competencies that will make them the agents of change much needed to deal with the climate change crisis. Thus, properly implemented climate change education can be one of the most effective mitigation measures with long-term effects. As complex as change is, so are the educational strategies employed in climate change education. Educational strategies are best designed when they are based on knowledge of the learners' level of knowledge and preconceptions (Fortner, 2001). Environmental information can be selected and experiences organized to fill known gaps, enhance understanding of relationships, and remediate misconceptions. Climate change has a direct impact on education. Because the primary impacts of climate change on education arise from the effects of extreme weather events, such as heavy rains accompanied by flash floods, strong winds and hail storms with short and long-term consequences (ZHDR (2017) .

Climate Change. The Earth's climate has always changed. Changes in the Earth's orbit, the energy output of the sun, volcanic activity, the geographic distribution of the Earth's land masses and other internal or external processes can influence climate. Scientists refer to this type of long-term climate change as "natural climate change". As a result of natural climate change, the Earth has experienced regular cold periods (or ice ages) in the past, when glaciers covered large parts of the Earth's surface. The Earth has also experienced warmer periods when sea levels were much higher than they are now. In the Earth's long-term history, the current period is characterized by a relatively warm, stable climate that has lasted since the end of the last ice age about 11,700 years ago. This period is known to geologists as the Holocene and is the period during which human civilization has flourished.

If this were the only type of climate change, then the interest to sociologists would be minimal. However, scientific observations and models indicate that the Earth's climate is now changing due to human activity. This is termed "anthropogenic climate change". The processes involved are complex but can be summarized. However, since the 1900s, anthropogenic activities have been the main driver of climate change, primarily due to the burning of fossils, like coal, oil and gas, to make electricity and power vehicles, converting forests for agriculture and cities, cultivating livestock, and release of "greenhouse gases" into the atmosphere. These gases include carbon dioxide (CO₂), methane (CH₄), ammonia (NH₂),

nitrous oxide (N₂O), chlorofluorocarbon (CFCs) and sulfur hexafluoride (SF₆). Other Fluorinated gases include Hydro-fluorocarbons (HFCs), Nitrogen trifluoride (NF₃), and Perfluorocarbons (PFCs). The main greenhouse gases (GHGs) are carbon dioxide, methane, halocarbons, and nitrous oxide.

However, Crowley, (2000) in Gazzaz & Aldeseet, (2021); Frigg et al., (2015) emphasizing on their findings that temperature increase in the 20th century was caused primarily by GHG and that our trust in the GHGs explain that the global warming is very high.. These gases accumulate in the atmosphere and allow radiation from the sun to pass through but trap some of the heat radiating back from the Earth, called the “greenhouse effect” because the principle is similar to a greenhouse, where the glass roof allows sunlight in but traps heat for growing plants. Over time, the enhanced greenhouse effect results in “global warming” - an increase in the Earth’s average temperature. Global warming is one type of climate change and it drives other changes in the climate, such as changes in rainfall patterns and the frequency and distribution of weather events such as droughts, storms, floods and heat waves. Although, the terms climate change and global warming are often used interchangeably. Climate change is a broader term that incorporates both global warming and other observed changes in climate. Many scientists have argued that the impacts of climate change will be devastating for natural and human systems and that climate change poses an existential threat to human civilization. A key question for sociologists, posed by Giddens (2011), is why a threat of such magnitude is routinely ignored by our societies? Giddens’ response, which he calls the “Giddens Paradox”, is that the lack of tangible, immediate danger from climate change means that most scientists will do nothing to respond. Yet by the time the danger becomes clearly visible, it will be too late to act due to the lag between the emission of greenhouse gases and their full warming impact. At the point where the danger becomes too great to ignore a further warming will be locked in by emissions already in the atmosphere. For many sociologists, finding a pathway out of this paradox is a key concern. Climate change is also of interest to sociologists because the activities that are responsible for anthropogenic climate change are embedded in human social life. Everyday social practices like eating, working, moving about, and heating and cooling our homes result in emissions of greenhouse gases that contribute to climate change. Further, the causes and impacts of climate change are unevenly distributed, raising questions of social justice. In general, wealthier countries produce more greenhouse gas emissions per person, whereas poorer countries tend to be more vulnerable to the impacts of climate change. Proposed responses to climate change also have social impacts that are unevenly distributed. Consequently, climate change poses the first truly global social dilemma, and it is one that has proven politically intractable at multiple governance scales. Numerous definitions of climate change (CC) are found in the literatures. Lineman et al. (2015); Gazzaz & Aldeseet, (2021) defined climate change as a change in global or regional climate patterns, in particular a change apparent from the mid to late 20th century on the increased level of atmospheric carbon dioxide arising from the use of fossil fuels. Riedy (2018) stated that climate change is the average of the weather conditions at a particular point on the Earth. Climate is expressed in terms of expected temperature, rainfall and wind conditions based on historical observations. Climate change is either a change in the average climate or climate variability that persists over an extended period.

The United Nations Climate Action (UNCA) defines climate change as a long-term shift in temperatures and weather patterns. Such shifts can be natural, due to changes in the sun’s activity or large volcanic eruption. The United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) defined Climate Change as ‘a change of climate which is attributed directly or indirectly to human activity that alters the composition of the global atmosphere and which in addition to natural climatic variability’ (Riedy 2018; Gazzaz & Aldeseet, 2021). Nepras et al., (2022) emphasized the power of humans to fundamentally change the landscape and the environment, and that the collapses of the ecosystems, such as agricultural systems or local climates have led to the weakening or destruction of entire empires. Similarly, and as a consequence of the changes, Nepras et al., (2022) stressed the emergence of war conflicts, population declines, and a general regression of cultural and social development and with human-induced climate change as another in a long line of consequences that the development of human civilization has brought about to date, impact of past environmental crises has mostly been local or regional. Life on Earth is

possible partly because some gases such as carbon dioxide (CO₂) and water vapor which naturally occur in Earth's atmosphere trap heat like the greenhouse gas. In a series of UN reports that thousands of scientists and government reviewers agreed that the limiting global temperature rise to no more than 1.5°C would help us avoid the worst climate impacts and maintain a livable climate. However, policies currently in place point to a 2.8°C temperature rise by the end of the century. Gazzaz and Aldesst (2021) in Odjugo (2010) and Falaye & Okwilagwe (2016) understood that climate change is caused by two factors. The bio-geographic factors, which encompass natural forces, are linked with human activities. The later encircle the emission of large gas quantities of GHGs into the atmosphere through fossil fuel burning, gas flaring, industrialization, biomass burning, animal farming, and solid waste incineration as well as human activities to reduce the amount of carbon that it absorbed from the atmosphere like deforestation (Gazzaz & Aldeseet, 2021). The emissions that cause climate change comes from every part of the world and affect everyone, but some countries produce much more than others, and the emitted GHGs are the major culprit for global warming (Odjugo, 2010; Wright & Boorse, 2012; Yang et al., 2018; Akrof et al, 2019; Gazzaz & Aldeseet, 2021).

Another historical causes of global climate change is that pollution has been a relatively local problem, but transboundary pollution (Ogbomah & Obiene, 2012) effecting a given river, lake, bay or slightly large area such as the air (Wright & Boorse, 2012). Presently, scientists are analyzing pollution on a global scale. For instance, concerning about the depletion of the stratospheric ozone layer Wright & Boorse, (2012) and that the concept has led to international action such as the Montreal Protocol in 1987 aimed at curbing pollution from the release of chlorofluorocarbon refrigerants into the atmosphere. The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) was established by the United Nations in 1988 and giving the responsibility to report its assessment of climate change at five year intervals (Olmos, 2001; Wright & Boorse, 2012). The latest of this is the Fourth Assessment Report (FAR) which was released in 2007.

The Primary School. The term "Primary Education" or "Elementary Education" is often the first stage of compulsory education coming between the first stage of compulsory and secondary education. Its aim is to create, establish and offer opportunities to all children regardless of age, gender or country of origin, to achieve a balanced cognitive, emotional psychomotor development. Every government particularly in the developed countries regulates primary education according to the Department of Education or supervising ministry for better curriculum implementation, and processes the standard of elementary schools to ensure students receives quality education regardless of the school they attend. Most States require children to receive a primary education to learn basic concepts. According to the United Nations, Children's Fund (UNICEF), providing children with this education has many positive effects, including, decreasing poverty, decreasing child mortality rates, encouraging gender equality, and increasing environmental concern. Primary school education provides students with fundamental skills that will build the foundation for the rest of their academic and career instructors teach students subject like mathematics, basic science, Language Arts, Social studies, History, Geography, Arts and Music.

Primary education institutions provide children with some of their opportunities to meet people from different religion, and socio-economic statuses as well as people with different disabilities. Therefore, primary school teachers have a unique chance to teach children about tolerance and respect. Students of this stage are taught basic life time skills like reading, writing, spellings, interpersonal communication and concentration. Elementary school students also learn good study habits including time management, multi-tasking and organization as well as test preparation. Primary school education instructors teach several different subjects to a group of students so they must constantly keep students engaged in learning. Teachers at this level use different tools to teach children and keep their attentions including games or sports, books, computers, etc. Because of the significance of primary education, it is studied up to doctorate philosophy in most universities world over. With the advent of specialization, literatures of primary education have been pouring in several journals (Havu-Nuutinen et al., 2010; Saminsky, 2011: Jenuwine, 2014; Carter, 2014; Currie & Ly, 2016; Asit, 2016 :). It is this reason that Jim & Kin (2024) advocated for the inclusion of climate change curriculum to primary 3-4 pupils. One of the challenges is

that there is no school subject or curriculum focusing on the environment or climate; thus, climate change is usually integrated and taught in other subjects such as science or social studies. Yet, its approach is often neglected or peripheral due to the heavy focus on disciplinary contents and curriculum outcomes.

Preparing climate change through Quality education. To respond to the needs of children most are at risk and marginalized by climate change. Quality education aims to make all girls and boys more resilient to the impacts of climate change. Quality education is a key component of adoptive capacity, the knowledge and the skills needed to adopt lives and livelihoods to the ecological, social and economic realities of changing environment. The child friendly school approach is most effective when child's life cycle and leads to lifelong learning in adulthood. For education to be transformative, it must be based on 1) active, inclusive and participatory learning and teaching processes, 2) supportive and qualified teachers, 3) Soft, supportive learning environment, and 4) inherent links to local communities and local issues.

While children are among the most vulnerable to climate change they need not be considered pensive or helpless victims. Through education projects and actions children can contribute to every aspect of climate change policy making mitigation and adaptation. Children are powerful agents of change and when empowered and educated on climate change by child friendly schools, children can reduce the vulnerabilities of themselves and their communities and contribute to sustainable development. According to the research (Lotus educating girls and women) is one of the best ways of strengthening community adaptation to climate change.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

Having described the contours of education as a product, the research emphasized the connection and denotations of educated persons and the need to train the primary school pupils for a sustainable educational development. The teacher at the primary school plays an important role in keeping and modeling the habits, good manners and character of the children. Including a viable curriculum on climate change at the level of primary school particularly those of 3, 4, and 5 will imbibe a culture to better mitigate issues of environmental vulnerability and adaptation in the ever growing population world over. The challenging notions of postponing climate change education until later grades will increase the danger of the already damaged environment and hence, emphasizing the importance of early engagement with climate change discourse is to bring about sustainable environment.

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